

TALENT MANAGEMENT – AN ETYMOLOGICAL STUDY

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(a scientific article)

Abstract:

The current article unveils and analyzes important shades of meaning for the widely discussed term ‚talent management‘. It not only grounds the outlined perspectives in incremental formulation and elaboration of this construct, but also is oriented to exploring the underlying reasons for the social actors, proposing new nuances. Thus, a mind map and a fish-bone diagram are constructed to depict effectively and efficiently the current state of development for talent management and make easier the realizations of future research endeavours in this field.

Keywords: talent management, human resource management, human capital management, corporate culture.

JEL: M12, M14, J24.

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